

1. Title of Dataset:

Supplementary figures and tables to manuscript entitled “Sex steroid levels in women with hypopituitarism: a case-controlled observational study”

2. Author Information:

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Supplemental Figure 1. DHEA and androstenedione levels in PRE-Y (A, B) and POST-O (C, D) women with HH, with and without ERT. Box boundaries represent 25th–75th percentile, horizontal bars represent median values, whiskers represent lowest/highest values that is not an outlier, and circles represent statistical outliers. No significant differences were seen between women with and without ERT (Mann-Whitney u-test). PRE-Y, premenopausal or younger (≤ 52 years). POST-O, postmenopausal or older (> 52 years). HH, hypogonadotropic hypogonadism. ERT, estrogen replacement therapy. Values $< \text{LLOQ}$ were set to $\text{LLOQ}/\sqrt{2}$ in the analysis.

Supplemental Figure 2. Testosterone and DHT levels in PRE-Y (A, B) and POST-O (C, D) women with HH, with and without ERT. Box boundaries represent 25th–75th percentile, horizontal bars represent median values, whiskers represent lowest/highest values that is not an outlier, and circles represent statistical outliers. No significant differences were seen between women with and without ERT (Mann-Whitney u-test). PRE-Y, premenopausal or younger (≤ 52 years). POST-O, postmenopausal or older (> 52 years). HH, hypogonadotropic hypogonadism. ERT, estrogen replacement therapy. Values $< \text{LLOQ}$ were set to $\text{LLOQ}/\sqrt{2}$ in the analysis.

Supplemental Table 1. Characteristics of HH women with and without ERT		
PRE-Y women with HH (n=26)		
	Without ERT (n=10) <i>From Table 1</i>	With ERT (n=16)
Age, years	48.0 (42.2-50.0)	39.5 (34.0–46.8)*
BMI, kg/m ²	31.0 (25.7–41.8)	26.6 (24.8–34.3)
TSH deficiency, n (%)	9 (90)	13 (81)
Diabetes insipidus, n (%)	4 (40)	3 (19)
LH, IU/L	1.5 (0-2.4)	0.2 (0-1.1)
FSH, IU/L	4.8 (0.3-6.6)	0.7 (0-2.2)*
Estradiol, pg/mL	5.1 (0-9.4)	21.9 (2.2-72.0)
Estrone, pg/mL	19.8 (0.6-25.7)	79.9 (15.0-341)*
SHBG, nmol/L	48.2 (30.2–77.8)	70.5 (47.5–126)
POST-O women with HH (n=56)		
	Without ERT (n=45) <i>From Table 1</i>	With ERT (n=11)
Age, years	68.0 (62.0–72.0)	60.0 (55.0–67.0)*
BMI, kg/m ²	28.6 (25.7–32.4)	28.2 (21.6–30.3)
TSH deficiency, n (%)	35 (78)	11 (100)
Diabetes insipidus, n (%)	10 (22)	2 (18)
LH, IU/L	0.8 (0.2-3.7)	1.1 (0-2.2)
FSH, IU/L	3.2 (1.5-13.5)	1.8 (0-4.4)
Estradiol, pg/mL	2.5 (0.6-5.1)	22.6 (4.0-35.5)***
Estrone, pg/mL	10.5 (1.7-18.8)	37.0 (15.2–140)**
SHBG, nmol/L	60.5 (39.3–85.3)	73.0 (58.0–98.0)

Characteristics of patients with hypopituitarism and HH with and without ERT at the time of the blood sampling. Data are median (interquartile (IQ) range) or n (%). Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; ERT, estrogen replacement therapy; FSH, follicle-stimulating hormone; HH, hypogonadotropic hypogonadism; LH, luteinizing hormone; POST-O, postmenopausal or older (>52 years) women; PRE-Y, premenopausal or younger (≤52 years) women; SHBG, sex hormone-binding globulin; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone. *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001 vs HH without ERT (Mann-Whitney U-test or Fisher's exact test).